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	D3.5 – REPORT ON THE GOVERNANCE PROCESS FOR INTEGRATION OF FUTURE SERVICES VERSION 1.0 –FINAL PUBLIC
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Report on the governance process for integration of future services

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Table of Contents

1. INTRODUCTION	6
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	7
3. METHODOLOGY AND DEMOGRAPHICS	9
4. MAIN THEMES	12
4.1 THE IMPORTANCE OF OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE AND PLATFORMS	12
4.2 THE IMPORTANCE OF USERS AS CONTRIBUTORS TO OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE OR PLATFORMS	13
4.3 HOW AND WHY SHOULD ONE CONTRIBUTE TO GOTRIPLE PLATFORM?	15
4.4 THE ROLE OF USERS IN SERVICE GOVERNANCE AND DECISION-MAKING	16
4.5 THE OWNERSHIP OF A PLUG-IN	18
5. OUTCOMES	19
5.1 SCENARIOS	20
5.2 USE CASES	25
6. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE GOVERNANCE OF FUTURE SERVICES	28
7. CONCLUSION	29
8. REFERENCES	30
9. APPENDIX	32

Acronyms

AU	University of Abertay
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
D3.1	Deliverable 3.1
D3.5	Deliverable 3.5
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EKT	Ethniko Kentro Tekmiriosis kai Ilektronikou Periechomenou
IBL-PAN	Instytut Badań Literackich Polskiej Akademii Nauk
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
T3.5	Task 3.5
UC	Universidade de Coimbra
UL-ADP	Slovenian Social Science Data Archives, University of Ljubljana
UX	Users Experience
WP3	Work Package 3

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Publishable Summary

The TRIPLE project will help social sciences and humanities (SSH) research in Europe to gain visibility, to be more efficient and effective, to improve reuse of research results within the SSH and beyond, and to dramatically increase their societal impact. By building the GoTriple platform, the European discovery solution, TRIPLE addresses these issues: it enables researchers to discover and reuse SSH data, but also to engage with other researchers and projects across disciplinary and language boundaries. The platform provides all the necessary means to build interdisciplinary projects and to develop large-scale scientific missions. It will thus increase the economic and societal impacts of SSH resources.

GoTriple will be a dedicated service of the OPERAS research infrastructure and is integrated in the EOSC Open Marketplace. The European Commission finances the project under the Horizon 2020 framework with 5.6 million Euros for a duration of 42 months.

Deliverable 3.5 reports on the work carried out in T3.5. The aim of this task was to explore the ways in which users can enrich the tools and services that are available in the GoTriple platform, and explore the appropriate governance processes for these user generated tools. To identify the possible solutions, Ten interviews and three webinars were conducted. Based on this data and the personas that were developed in task 3.1 and are presented in D3.1, five scenarios and use cases were created in order to highlight the ways in which plug-ins or new resources should be incorporated in the GoTriple platform.

The work reported in this deliverable will help the TRIPLE consortium to realise and establish the best possible procedures for cooperating with users in order to enrich the services of the GoTriple platform and make it relevant to even more members of the SSH community or to other interested parties.

1| INTRODUCTION

GoTriple is a multilingual digital platform that provides a single access point to discover and reuse open scholarly SSH resources and find peers. It has been conceived from the beginning as a user-centred platform, and for that reason the approach that has been followed for its design is the co-design one. With this approach, the participation of users in designing the platform is highly valued; community-driven innovation and the inclusion of voices that are outside the inner circle of the developers of a platform are deemed necessary for the effectiveness and sustainability of the platform.

In the light of this, it is no surprise that the users of the GoTriple platform are encouraged to actively contribute to the extension of the services that the platform provides, as well as to the enrichment of its resources. This means that users will have the opportunity to propose the integration of existing software or resources to the platform, or to create software and plug-ins themselves, in order to enlarge the scope of the platform's functionalities on the one hand, and to make the platform more relevant and useful to their own research on the other.

This report explores the ways in which users can contribute to the extension of the services of the platform. It also identifies the governance procedures that should be followed in order to integrate these services in the platform. What should be the right procedures and criteria for adopting potential plug-ins or resources in the GoTriple? What should be the governance of these extensions? D3.5 main goal is to address these and other similar questions, in order to identify the workflow in evaluating the usefulness of an extension and the feasibility of its integration in the platform, as well as the models that are appropriate for the governance of these extensions. D3.5 is the outcome of the work that has been conducted in Task 3.5 *Governance process for enabling integration of future services*.

In order to form informed recommendations for the governance and integration of future extensions of the platform that the users will suggest, EKT has created scenarios and use cases related to the integration and governance of the new services. The basis for the discussions that took place was a structured questionnaire constructed by EKT, which can be found as an appendix at the end of this report. For the construction of the scenarios we exploited the input of the research conducted for this task (T 3.5), and the personas that were created for Task 3.1 and are presented in D3.1. Five scenarios and an equal number of use cases were developed to reflect the results of the research.

The structure of the deliverable is the following:

- A literature review regarding the co-design and governance of e-infrastructures.
- A description of the methodology adopted for the research conducted for T3.5 and details on the interviews conducted.
- Discussion on the main themes that emerged from this research.

- Presentation of Scenarios and Use Cases.
- Recommendations for the Governance of Future Services.
- A conclusion that reflects the findings of the research.

2 | LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section we will briefly discuss the literature that is relevant to the research of T3.5. The aim of this task is to collect feedback about how users themselves could extend the existing services of the GoTriple platform, and about the governance models of future services. In order to have a clear idea on these topics, we referred to the literature related to user experience (UX), the co- design of e-platforms, and the governance models of e-infrastructures.

In the last decade the UX approach was implemented not only in various industries, but also in scholarly services development, such as online library catalogues (Appleton, 2016; Priestner & Borg, 2016; Scupola & Zanfei, 2016). Any infrastructure, service or product designed for the academic community should make decisions informed by the community's requirements (though naming those does not only have to depend upon what users search for, but also what knowledge they should actually gain) (Boukhelifa et al., 2018; Hjørland, 2013; Kim Wu & Lanclos, 2011; Maryl et al., 2020). Different methodologies of UX research are also applied to the development of SSH research infrastructures (Boukhelifa et al., 2018; Brown et al., 2006; Maryl et al., 2020; Van Zundert, 2012). Involving various users from the wide SSH community into the design of the services created for their benefit is a crucial challenge. Researchers and other stakeholders of the SSH community are usually in a less advantageous position than others, because arguably SSH has been behind other disciplines in the incorporation of digital tools (Avanço et al., 2021). As a result, despite technological advances in the area of non-commercial IT services for academic purposes, Google seems to be the most widely used tool in discovery among humanists and social scientists (Adema & Rutten, 2010; Avanço et al., 2021). SSH researchers in their daily business are already dependent on such tools like Zotero (referencing and knowledge organisation), different digital archives or publishers' discovery services (Avanço, 2021). However, more advanced digital skills, typical for digital humanities, such as knowledge of programming languages and softwares, are still rare and require certain specialisation to master them. Still, due to the rise of digital humanities, understood not only as a new approach to humanist research, but also a discipline focused on developing research infrastructures for specific academic communities, new roles have emerged in those communities as well (Anderson 2013, Edmond, 2020). In the TRIPLE WP3 T3.5 we researched professionals with such a dual experience in order to gain their insights regarding efficient governance model for future GoTriple maintenance purposes and its integration with other tools and infrastructures (Edwards et al., 2007; Schafer & Wieneke, 2021). Given the complexity of the questions asked (such as governance principles for research infrastructures) most of the

interviewees were persons with background in the development process of tools or infrastructures.

A close 'knowledge exchange between digital humanities developers and researchers' is said to be one of the necessary conditions helping create deep synergies between those groups, allowing for providing truly useful tools for the research community (van Zundert 2012, p. 20). Such online projects' development and maintenance require involvement of both digital specialists and experienced researchers during the design and implementation phases of project development (Brown et al. 2006). One of the first challenges the tool and the development team need to face appears after launching the product when it lands in the "real world" of users. Only then its usefulness and attractiveness are truly tested (Kim Wu & Lanclos, 2011). The traditional user-centred design approach (mainly used to develop products) is not sufficient for the products's maintenance and governance purposes. The ideas of 'service design' and 'interaction design' and practices, such as 'design for sustainability' or 'design for transforming' are trying to address various needs and require a longer-term viewpoint to be taken (Sanders & Stappers, 2008). Therefore the TRIPLE project design methodology is based on the co-design approach (Sanders & Stappers, 2008), which emphasises the participatory character of design and heavily draws from user experience research in all phases of the product creation. As it was noticed in the TRIPLE D3.4 (Andreini & Forbes, 2021), co-operative design method does not necessarily involve actual design but also brings up the importance of improving users' technological skills. The GoTriple team plans to incorporate users into the next phases of the platform's development: the integration of other applications and the maintenance of the product. Since the task has been conducted after the launch of the beta version of the platform, the interviewees were able to test the platform's features and functionalities and relate their needs and ideas to the actual product.

Research infrastructures and e-infrastructures are particularly important today as many diverse digital resources, online tools, and technical solutions have emerged (Anderson, 2013; Edwards et al., 2007; Maryl et al., 2020). This has led to a growing need for them to be harmonised, organised, integrated (Anderson 2013; Edmond 2020). Successful maintenance of infrastructures requires developing a governance model (Maijer et al 2012). Governance is an elusive term applied by diverse disciplines from management studies to sociology of innovation and others. The governance model for research infrastructures plays a crucial role in their 'to be or not to be' (Edmond 2020). She provides the example of DARIAH-EU to argue that its structure, organised as a marketplace of tools, decided over DARIAH's relevant success among other similar projects established a decade ago (Edmond 2020, p. 219). DARIAH is based on an in-kind contribution of its members and its governance system is participatory since each member contributes to the infrastructures' marketplace offer.

There are governance theorisations and models tested and analysed in the literature which can be related to the GoTriple future development (Gisselquist, n.d.; Schafer & Wieneke, 2021; Scupola & Zanfei, 2016). One of them is the network governance model. It emphasises the role of community-driven innovation and argues for including voices from the outside in the service development process (Scupola & Zanfei, 2016). The inclusive characteristic of the new

governance models was also recommended by the United Nations. According to their paper, good governance of web-based projects is dependent on eight major values: participation, accountability, consensus, transparency, responsiveness, effectiveness and efficiency, equity and inclusiveness, and lastly rule of law (United Nations, n.d.). Those values are similar to those adopted by the OPERAS consortium and recommended by open science practitioners (Edmond, 2020; Maryl et al., 2020; Schafer & Wieneke, 2021).

Another assumption, brought up by practitioners, is that governance is a multistakeholder process and requires teams of professionals with diverse backgrounds (Welchman 2015). Driven from the technology industry, a successful governance model for IT solutions assumes establishing a digital team, consisting of various stakeholders, which is separate from the executive board of the organisation (Györy et al., 2012; Meijer et al., 2012). Depending on how large a community we are capable of building, the interviewees of Task 3.5. could be a part of it as secondary stakeholders. Including users with various backgrounds into the development process and maintenance of the tool is not only in compliance with crucial values of web solutions design and governance. It is also a remedy for insufficiency of accountability and transparency which often comes up in the process of professionalisation of the service.

3 | METHODOLOGY AND DEMOGRAPHICS

For T3.5 we conducted 10 interviews and 3 webinars in total over the period April 2022 - July 2022. The aim of these interviews and webinars was the creation of scenarios and use cases that will help us form recommendations for the integration and governance of extensions, suggested by users, to the existing services of the GoTriple platform. The script of the interviews and the webinars were developed in January-February 2022. An initial draft provided by the task leader (EKT) was commented on by WP leader (AU) and by other partners before reaching the final, agreed draft (reported in the Appendix). Interviews and webinars have been conducted remotely, using conference-call software (MS Teams). Informed consent was collected before the interview, by asking the interviewees to send a scanned and signed copy of the consent form back to the interviewers. Webinar participants who registered via a web form were asked instead to fill in a web consent form before participating in the data collection events.

Partners EKT and IBL-PAN were involved in conducting the interviews and organising the webinars. Several other project partners were also involved in supporting the identification of participants for the interviews. All of the interviews and webinars have been conducted in English, recorded and then transcribed before their analysis. For the analysis of the data, we used Thematic Analysis method. We selected this approach because it allows us to identify recurring themes and patterns. Based on the personas that were created for D3.1 with Thematic analysis as well, we created the scenarios and use cases that are the main outcome of

this work. With an initial thematic analysis we identified recurring themes. After that we re-analysed the data in order to consolidate these themes so that we can have in our disposal a core set of themes we could use as a base in order to produce the scenarios and the use-cases. The themes that emerged from the analysis are presented in the following section.

Both interviews and webinars were structured to address the issues that are important for the users of a discovery platform, and people who are interested and willing to contribute to the further development of such a platform by proposing extension of its services. Key themes included aspects such as:

- Importance of discovery platforms in general and open source in particular
- The importance of users as contributors to a platform or a software
- The role of users in the decision making
- Possible contribution to the GoTIPLE platform
- The ownership of a plug-in

From the beginning of the task, we were aware that several problems could arise in the enrollment of participants. Apart from the inherent issues that were discussed in other deliverables of WP3, such as D3.1 (Forbes et al 2020) (the huge variety in SSH research, wide geographical spread, and the different career levels of potential interviewees and webinar participants), there was an additional one for T 3.5: the research participants, at least some of them, should, in principle, have the capability to contribute to the extension of the existing services of the GoTriple platform, by proposing plug-ins or other types of resources. That means that the profile should be, at least to some degree, technically oriented. For this case, we looked for participants that were potentially: SSH researchers with a technical background, programmers who are familiar with SSH, digital humanists, information scientists, etc. Many of the participants in the research we conducted have what we could say a “dual identity”, as they are active researchers in SSH and also work on research infrastructures or as developers.

We developed a reasonable map for the sampling, mainly as a guide to ensure that interviewees were not recruited with e.g. overrepresentation of the same country or the same discipline. In these terms we sought to reach a reasonable balance of representation among: (1) the location in relation to South Europe, North Europe and Central/Eastern Europe, (2) the gender and (3) the discipline area. Moreover, we prepared a reasonable sampling plan for the career level. Ultimately the enrolment of interviewees and webinars participants has been based on the availability of people and contacts of the project partners, and in many occasions contacts were made (following the sampling plan) but interviews could not then be performed, because the potential interviewee was not available and we needed to approach other potential interviewees. In the end, the goal of interviewing 10 representatives of the broader SSH community was successfully met.

The demographics of the academic interviewees is presented in Table 1. We had 19 people participating in the research. The participants of this survey are based in the following countries: Italy, Portugal, Serbia, and Greece (as South Europe), Germany, Poland and France (as East and Central Europe), UK, Norway (as North Europe), and Mexico, Brazil and Canada as participants outside Europe. We have interviewed researchers from the following disciplines (broadly defined): Philosophy, Digital Architecture, Literature, Digital Humanities, Software development, Information Science, Cultural Heritage Management, Ancient Literature, Artificial Intelligence, Librarianship, History, Philology, Archeology.

TABLE 1. INTERVIEWS AND WEBINARS

Job Role	Gender	Country of Affiliation
Information Scientist	Female	Portugal
Digital Architect	Male	Portugal
PhD Student	Female	Poland
Researcher	Male	UK
Software Developer	Female	Poland
Digital Humanities Librarian	Female	Mexico
Digital Humanist	Male	Italy
Digital Heritage Management	Female	Greece
Data Scientist	Male	Germany
AI expert	Male	UK
Librarian	Female	Italy
Librarian	Male	Brazil
PhD Student	Male	Canada
Librarian	Female	Serbia
Information Scientist	Female	Serbia
Digital Humanist	Male	France
Researcher	Male	Norway

Computer Scientist	Male	Norway
Researcher	Male	Portugal

4 | MAIN THEMES

In this section, we present some of the core themes and patterns that emerged from the interviews and webinars. These issues enlightened the discussion that took place via the interviews and webinars and provided the framework for analysing the data (interviews and webinars) and constructing use cases and validation scenarios. While the profiles of the participants in this research are quite divergent, their views seem to align in most of the major issues that emerged. This does not mean that all the participants agreed on everything. Although not all of the following issues could be incorporated in the construction of scenarios and use cases, effort was made to include the ones which are most relevant for a discovery platform like GoTriple, in this process.

4.1 The importance of open source software and platforms

The vast majority of the participants in the research for T3.5 were familiar with using platforms and more specifically open source platforms. They use bibliographic data management software (e.g. Zotero), open source repository solutions (e.g. DSpace), Open Journal Systems etc. Some of them have contributed to the development of open source software or platforms like open source components of data aggregators, or local chapters for programming languages like R, or platforms for the encoding of texts or documents.

All of the participants agreed on **the importance of having open source software and platforms**, as the following excerpt shows:

"I believe that openness is a value per se. I think that if you want to build, if you want to use the technology that we have, openness is a value." (Italy, Digital Humanist)

First, for deontological reasons since all of them are strongly inclined towards open science. They firmly believe that the SSH community cannot rely on options which are created outside the community and cannot be controlled by the community. In addition, the open source option facilitates the creation of new solutions (software, platforms, etc.). If there is a community that is dedicated to open source, all the ideas about a code can be embraced by the community and this can lead to the implementation of new ideas faster, and in a more effective way.

However, there are also pragmatic reasons for preferring open source software and platforms. People who work on digital humanities need to have free access to platforms, at the point of use. This will allow them to find the data they search for and the tools they need to manipulate this data. The relevant tools must be built having interoperability in mind and, for doing this, they have to be designed for open access.

As a participant puts it:

“Mathematical formulas are used by computers to gain information. If I do not know what kind of formulas to use and if I don't know how the calculation is being made, I have little understanding of what actually happens” (Data Scientist, Germany).

Another interesting aspect of the discussion regarding usefulness of open source platforms is the following: besides the broad access to resources, open source platforms are important for data preservation reasons as well. This is well captured by the following excerpt:

“We need to assure that information that we are producing will be available in future. I think that we also have to have preservation issues in mind”. (Information Scientist, Portugal)

Some of the participants highlighted the fact there are some prerequisites for successfully imposing the open source paradigm. The most important of them is that there has to be a large enough community able to support the development and the maintenance of an open source platform itself. Others have pointed out the fact that open source doesn't mean free, and this is something that we must have in mind when we are talking about open source platforms.

4.2 The importance of users as contributors to a platform or a software

All of the participants agreed that it is very **important for the users to have the opportunity to contribute to the development of platforms and open source software**. After all, such a software or a platform is built in order to satisfy users' needs. Therefore, it is very important when someone develops a software to have users in mind and, if possible, to engage users in this process. This is considered as the basis of the open source development, and without this not much can be developed, as clearly evidenced by the following quote from an interview:

“If users don't like a software, they will not use it. So I think it's very important to have users in mind and in fact to have users contributing to development of things that we want them to adopt”. (Information Scientist, Portugal)

A conclusion from this consideration is that users can support the process of developing open source software in many ways. A few participants claimed that there are examples similar to the GoTriple platform that were developed without that kind of an engagement from the community and they turned out to be not so effective operationally:

“So, I believe that users can support the process of developing Open source software in many ways. And actually, what is my experience with IT people is that sometimes actually very often they don't understand the context. It takes an effort for them to understand what is actually required and that's why people like myself are valuable in this process. We have examples of similar platforms that were developed without that kind of an engagement from the community and from librarians, and they are less functional than our platform”. (Information Scientist, Serbia).

Every user has his or her own way of using a software, his or her own research scenario and playing it out often leads to the identification of errors in the operation of the platform. Reporting these errors can help developers find possible improvements they did not have in mind in the first place. Such contributions can offer new perspectives for a software or a platform, which will increase their usage and will keep them sustainable. In the light of this, users want to have the opportunity to contribute to the development of a platform in order to make it more functional according to their needs.

The developers that took part in this research also admitted that it is important for them to have feedback from the users when they create a tool, for various reasons. Users can inform developers about new tools that they use and other initiatives that exist. Also, developers need to know what works properly according to user needs and, and if modifications are needed, what would be the nature of these modifications.

A clear outcome of this research is that in order to have the best possible results, and to transform the expectations of users into real products there has to be a responsible dialogue between software and platform developers on the one hand and researchers on the other. This dialogue may have some obstacles as programmers and researchers often do not “speak the same language” and they often struggle to communicate effectively. For example, SSH researchers may face difficulties in explaining to IT people what exactly they need, while IT people on the other hand may get frustrated when they try to explain to SSH researchers what is feasible or not. What is comforting here is that there are people who can act as a bridge between these two categories of people, and many from the TRIPLE Consortium who will continue to support the interactions around the platform.

A problem that has to be addressed in this respect is the enrollment of researchers in this process, due to issues like the following: Will the researchers have the time to get interested in a software? Will they take the time to get back to platform developers with feedback? It is one thing to say that something doesn't work properly– which does not help the development team—and it is another thing to have propositions about how it could work better.

4.3 How and why should one contribute to the GoTRIPLE platform?

A first kind of contribution that most of the participants discussed was the importance of pointing out alterations or additions that could be made to the platform to the developers and administrators of the platform, so that it can operate properly and sufficiently. One such proposition for example, among others, is the connection of ORCID to the GoTriple platform. In general the interviewees will be very happy to support the development of the platform by providing specifications for the platform. Also, many participants indicated that one way they can contribute is to form a group of regular users of the GoTriple platform and contribute by reporting bugs in the interface of the platform.

Other participants reported that they would be very interested in extending the resources that the GoTriple platform offers to its users. For example, users have their own sets of data they analyse via interfaces. For instance, they pull out their catalogue data and analyse it, or make the connection to software like Zotero or CITAVI. There are users who are very much interested in constructing software that helps them to manage their references, while this software could be later used by other users too for analysing their own data. .

The GoTriple platform is going to be multilingual. Many of the participants in this research said they are willing to contribute to this aspect of multilingualism by creating their own software in a way that the GoTriple can also use it as a plugin, as the following quote from an interview shows:

“We are interested as a team to create this custom software. We would like to contribute with the multilingualism stuff, to create something that can help in the strategy or this topic.” (Digital Architect, Portugal)

Another way to contribute to the extension of the GoTriple platform, as suggested by the participants, is to provide new resources that can enrich the platform. One relevant example is the enrichment of the GoTriple vocabulary. Participants have told us that they would happily volunteer to translate the controlled vocabulary to languages that do not belong to operational languages of the GoTriple platform, which are currently ten (Croatian, English, French, German, Greek, Italian, Polish, Portuguese, Spanish, Ukrainian). In the same direction they suggested that they can propose more specific terms about the search with thematic sources focusing on specific terms and on nonspecific terms in keywords, for example.

But why would people contribute to the extension of the GoTriple platform and of the services it provides? All of the participants expressed their commitment to Open Science, so for them the main incentive for contributing to this cause is that this way they have the opportunity to offer a service to the goal of Open Science:

“I think that regarding motivation, we don't have any other motivation but open science. We are in Europe and we have to do most of those efforts to be open to sharing and so on.” (Librarian, Italy).

Nevertheless, some of the participants hold the view that the users who contribute to the extension of the GoTriple platform must have a proper mention somewhere on the platform, probably a sign (a badge or a star) in their profile which indicates that they have contributed in a way.

While some of the participants stressed that there is no need for awarding special credentials to users that contribute to the GoTriple platform (for them contributing to the open source and open access initiative is enough), there are participants that see that contributing to the extension of the platform would be a very good way to enhance their CV.

To conclude on this matter, the key finding is that **all of the participants have declared that the primary value that guides their action is the need to be part of a community that is dedicated to Open Science** and to contribute to open source software and platforms.

4.4 The role of users in service governance and decision-making

The participants in this research expressed their views about how the governance of the plug-ins or the extensions of the services should be done. An issue that was discussed thoroughly in the interviews and the webinars was the procedure that must be followed and adopted by GoTriple in order to decide whether a proposed extension should be integrated in the platform.

The Gotriple platform is a user-centred infrastructure and the contributions of the users are more than welcome, but at the same time its maintenance is very demanding, so there has to be a filtering regarding the plug-ins that will be incorporated in the platform. This filtering also has to take into account the quality of the plug-ins and whether they are contributing to some kind of priority for the GoTriple community. There must be a procedure which ensures that extensions and plug-ins will be useful to a large part of the community and that they will add value to the GoTriple platform. In brief, it is essential to have a procedure in place to govern the additions of plugins to the main platform, i.e. for deciding if a plug-in should be accepted and incorporated in the platform or not. Moreover, this procedure needs to be transparent about who are the people that will be responsible for leading this procedure and for taking the decision.

For the purpose of our analysis we considered that there are two types of large groups or communities that are engaged in this procedure and can have a role in the decision-making: end

users and experts. Experts can be IT experts or experts in platforms' governance. This categorization enables us to pose questions that can provoke extremely interesting answers for our research. Should both of these categories have a say on this? If yes, should their opinions carry the same weight?

All of the participants agree that the procedure of decision-making should have a hybrid character. The combined wisdom of experts and end-users will provide the conditions for the best possible outcome of this procedure. Nevertheless, they do not all agree on the role of each category in this process.

Some respondents stated that if these opinions don't have the same weight an inequality between these two categories would be created. The existence of such inequality would be against the proper operation of an open source community. It is acknowledged that experts are proficient in what they do regarding technical matters, but on the other hand if an open source tool doesn't have a community, it is just a handy, sophisticated machine that no one uses and no one updates.

On the other hand, experts are essential as they have the knowledge and expertise to validate the technical aspects or the governance aspects of a proposed plug-in. As several participants highlighted, users often ask the creation of things that are not feasible or not worth the try, or they have a very limited scope and will be of interest for a very limited audience. The inherent danger will be that users will start proposing a large number of very specific things, and this will be very problematic. The group of experts must include people who represent members of the TRIPLE Consortium, as these people know better the operation of the platform, but the presence of highly prestigious experts of the broader community (digital humanists, SSH researchers, programmers) is recommended as this would make the procedure of decision making more inclusive and efficient.

Regarding the workflow required to decide about which plug-ins are eligible for being incorporated in the GoTriple platform, the hybrid model that we referred to is reflected in the following way: For the first stage a community driven channel or another form of online community can be used for the exchange of opinions between users, about the needs of the community. This discussion, in a free form, is the best way for new ideas to emerge. Having dedicated channels for such communications is considered to be very important.

All of the participants agreed that, after the proposition for a plug-in has been made, a committee will have the responsibility to decide if this plug-in should be incorporated to the GoTriple platform or not. The research indicated that there are two issues of concern regarding the people that should constitute this committee. The first has to do with users' participation in it. Should users have a say on this procedure or should only experts (i.e. IT experts or governance experts) participate? All of the participants agreed that the opinion of the users is important but not all agreed on the degree of relevance. For some of the people interviewed, the votes of users and experts must carry the same weight, while for others, experts and

especially experts that develop and maintain the GoTriple platform are the people who should have the authority to decide if a proposed extension should be integrated.

“First of all, if they (experts and users) do not have the same weight, this creates an inequality. In my opinion this goes against open source and the community.” (Digital Humanist, Italy)

“Maybe it's good also to include the users in the decision making, but maybe the experts' voice would be more important than the regular user vote. It's hard to say.” (Software Developer, Poland).

The other issue is if the committee should be made up only of experts that are part of TRIPLE or if experts outside the TRIPLE consortium should be part of this too. All the participants agreed that the TRIPLE consortium must have the final word on these matters since they have to maintain the platform ultimately, but external experts can ensure that there will be a broader view and evaluation of the proposed services.

Many participants in this research suggested that after the first acceptance a period of trial would be useful to decide if the plug-in is indeed useful. After a period of testing users may have the opportunity to vote and decide if a plug-in is valuable for the community. If the community of users decides that the proposed plug-in or extension is not useful or that it concerns only a small number of people it can be removed and no longer be a part of the platform.

In conclusion we can say that there is a tension that has to be carefully treated. On the one hand, a very controlled selection of plug-ins and their governance may discourage people from proposing a plug-in. On the other hand, some users may not realise the cost and the effort that is needed in order to build and maintain a platform, so, in some cases, their proposals may be utopian. It will therefore be **important for the GoTriple governance on new tools to strike the appropriate balance between these two positions: ensuring users' involvement, whilst ensuring the process is manageable and delivers results that can be of benefit for a large part of the user base.**

4.5 The ownership of a plug-in

Another issue that arose from the discussion is **the ownership of the plug-ins and the possible extensions**. As already mentioned, the participants in this research have a strong commitment to Open Science and open source software and platforms. In parallel to this there is the issue of intellectual property and ownership of the software created as a plug-in, or who can benefit from this service.

Two views emerged from interviews and webinars. One is that the creator must own the plug-in and may have a benefit of it in the future, but most of the interviewees hold the view that such a software or service should be part of the GoTriple platform and be open without restrictions of use. Most participants also stated that to the extent that we are talking about services

(European, national services) that are funded by taxpayers' money, commercialization should not be a goal.

What came out of the discussions was that the best way to tackle the problem of ownership is to have licences like Creative Commons which allows people to share their work and their contribution in a way that is open and the reuset is free for the entire community.

Of course there are difficulties, especially in cases when the plug-in might be developed by an institution that is not able to transfer the copyrights to anybody else because of some internal regulations. In any case, as participants suggested, there is no "one size that fits all". In cases like the one just mentioned it may be possible to have a different licence for different components of the platform, and there is no need to have only one type of licence.

"I think they should be open. They should have an open source licence. You know, something like "Apache 2.0"." (UK, AI expert)

"It could really be helpful to use creative common licence because they provide certain elements that can be combined and it would give a chance to make things open without having only a single option." (Data Scientist, Germany).

5 | OUTCOMES

In this section we will present the main outcomes of this research. These are the scenarios and use cases that have been produced in order to highlight the ways that users can contribute to the GoTriple platform and the procedures that must be followed for the proposed plug-ins to be incorporated to the platform. For the construction of the scenarios and use cases we will reuse some of the personas that were created for Task 3.1. Full overview of these personas can be found in D3.1.

As mentioned in D3.1, scenarios are narratives of the personas interacting with the platform and are fundamental for capturing the user perspective. Current design research considers their relevance in a number of areas. **Use cases**, on the other hand, will help us describe the ways that the users will interact with the platform in proposing new services, and the procedures by which these services should be governed.

5.1 Scenarios

Scenario 1: Integration of an existing open source software

Professor Julien Martin

AGE: 49

ACADEMIC POSITION: Senior Lecturer

DISCIPLINE: French Literature

NATIONALITY: French

WORKING IN: Sorbonne Université

Julien is not very used to working with digital technologies. He is worried that he is left behind with technology use. Recently, however, he started to use with some success the GoTriple platform to discover publications on French Literature.

He is having difficulties in organising the bibliography that he finds in the GoTriple platform, and he is frustrated with this. Discussing the problems that he faces with his colleagues, he finds out that there is open source software that facilitates the organisation of bibliography. He would be keen to see some of this software interfaced or incorporated in GoTriple.

Julien fills in a form that is available in Go Triple for proposing possible extensions or plug-ins to the existing GoTriple services. A group of experts of the TRIPLE Consortium makes a first inquiry and decides that Zotero could be a possible plug-in for the GoTriple platform.

Consortiums starts a discussion in a dedicated forum of the GoTriple community to find out whether Zotero could prove useful for other users. After a short period of time in which users presented their views for and against integrating Zotero in the GoTriple platform, a vote takes place. Most of the participants in the discussion highlighted the fact that Zotero is an open source platform that is widely used by most of them and this plays a major role in their decision.

The users of the platform voted in favour of integrating Zotero in the platform, and work starts for this integration. After a couple of months the integration is complete and now Julien is happy to be able to use a software that helps him organise his work.

The TRIPLE project is funded by the European Commission, under Grant Agreement No. 863420

Scenario 2: Integrating new resources

Dr. Ben Dubois

AGE: 30

ACADEMIC POSITION: Junior Lecturer

DISCIPLINE: European History (Modern)

NATIONALITY: French

WORKING IN: Paris-Sud University

Ben is part of an international network of researchers that work on European History. Whilst working with colleagues from the network, he often talks to them about the potential of the GoTriple platform, and how its use facilitates his research. He is eager to involve his colleagues in using GoTriple more often.

Ben works often with Milica, a historian from Serbia. They collaborate on a project regarding the Resistance during World War II. Serbian resources are not represented in the GoTriple platform. This makes the use of the platform a bit redundant for Milica, since many of the resources she works with are of national origin. She tells Ben that she would be keen to use GoTriple but that she would like to see some Serbian resources aggregated to the platform. Ben wants to support Milica and decides to contact the Serbian national repository which collects and preserves the relevant content in order to investigate the possibility of offering their resources as an extension to the existing resources of the platform. Milica also contacts the chief information scientist of the library of her institution in order to investigate the possibility of translating the GoTriple Vocabulary to their own language. This would allow Serbian users to use the search functionality of the platform in their own language .

Ben then makes a proposition to the GoTriple governance team for the inclusion of these resources. The GoTriple Governance team holds a meeting and the members evaluate the feasibility of including these resources in GoTriple. Experts of the governance team consider this feasible. After a discussion a vote is cast and the majority approves the decision to accept the extension of the existing resources, both the content resources and the GoTriple Vocabulary.

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Scenario 3: Integrating a new, community-built service

Carolina Weber

AGE: 23

ACADEMIC POSITION: PhD Student

DISCIPLINE: Social Science/ Politics

NATIONALITY: German

WORKING IN: University of Hamburg

Carolina's research is very multi-interdisciplinary. For the research she is currently conducting, she would like a visualisation which can offer a broad overview of how different disciplines have treated the same topics. Ideally this visualisation should come without a top-down classification logic. This kind of logic is not suitable for her purpose.

Carolina finds the visualisation service of the GoTriple platform very useful, but for her work she needs some additional specifications to it. She enters the forum of the GoTriple community to see if other users face the same problems and are interested in a similar service. From the discussion in the forum it emerges that more people are interested in such a plug-in.

The next step is to be decided whether this extension will be created by an external programmer or a company for a fee, or if the community has the capacity to take over this task. Although the members of the community are preoccupied with their own projects, a number of them offer their service in order to work for an open source solution that derives from the community, without a fee.

The GoTriple Governance Team issues a call seeking volunteers to create this plug-in. A group of not so senior level programmers and coders volunteers for the task. They do this for two reasons: The one is that they highly value the opportunity to belong to a community and help solve the problems that community faces, and the other is that if they solve this problem, it will be a very good addition to their CV. The only thing they want is proper credits for their work and acknowledgements from the GoTriple platform. For this reason they are willing to release their software with a CC BY licence.

The GoTriple Governance Team assigns a group of TRIPLE experts the task to evaluate the plug-in created by this group of programmers. After the evaluation procedure the task group confirms that the plug-in has the necessary quality to be part of the GoTriple services.

In the end, a new open source service is integrated in the GoTriple platform.

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Scenario 4: User-made plug-in

Dr. Christos Sideris

AGE: 36

ACADEMIC POSITION: Lecturer

DISCIPLINE: Computational Linguistics

NATIONALITY: Greek

WORKING IN: University of Thessaloniki

For furthering his research, Christos needs an open access dataset he can re-use in his research. He has identified a set of data that is available and freely accessible through the GoTriple platform. In order to be able to manipulate and interpret this data, Christos however has to create a set of ad-hoc scripts that he can use. He works on this for a while until the software reaches a good level of maturity.

Christos realises that this software could be of interest for others and that it could be used by other users of the GoTriple platform. He wonders if this could become a permanent plug-in of the GoTriple platform. As an advocate of Open Science, he creates an open source version of the software so other users can further build on this.

Christos is not sure if the software that he has created is good enough to be part of the GoTriple platform, but colleagues that have used it encourage him to file in a form which is available in GoTriple. The form will reach the GoTriple Governance Team and they will discuss whether to accept his software as a platform plug-in.

A committee of experts consisting of members of the TRIPLE Consortium is formed in order to assess the usefulness and viability of this plug-in. Experts outside the TRIPLE community are also called to contribute to this task. The committee asserts that the plug-in could be a useful extension of the services of the GoTriple platform. They decide to put it in operation for a trial period. After six months, the plug-in has a large number of uses, while the users provide positive feedback about its usefulness and operability.

The software has been successfully integrated in the services of the GoTriple platform.

The TRIPLE project is funded by the European Commission, under Grant Agreement No. 863420

Scenario 5: Integrating a proprietary software

Ms Maria Masthoff

AGE: 42

POSITION: Advisor to Policy Makers

WORKING IN: Netherlands (Based in Brussels)

Maria is an advisor to EU policy makers for socio-economic issues impacting Europe. For her work she needs accurate data in a form that allows her to make queries, to retrieve the information she needs, and in addition to make a visual representation of data from different sources.

Maria searches in the GoTriple platform for datasets that will help in the inquiry she is currently doing for how European societies are adapting to the post-covid era. She finds the visual representation service of the GoTriple platform very useful, but she needs an extension to the service that will help her exploit further the data she is collecting.

Maria starts to search for some useful software for this. Maria finds out about SPARNatura, a Javascript component which allows users to navigate data in a knowledge graph. She decides to propose the incorporation of SPARNatura in GoTriple. She fills the form that is available on GoTriple for proposing plug-ins or extensions to the platform, and starts a discussion in the dedicated forum in order to seek further support from the user community and understand any potential objection.

Although most of the participants in the discussion agree that the proposed software will be useful, they have objections because it is licensed under BSD Licence, which is an open source licence, but it does not guarantee the end user's complete freedom in the use of the software, since some derivative work may then become proprietary software. The preference of the GoTriple user community seems for plug-ins that are entirely open source solutions, and which guarantee that the software will always be open.

The GoTriple Governance committee, consisting of experts and users, decides that openness is a value per se for this community. This means that the fact that SPARNatura is not entirely open source software is a reasonable cause to reject its integration in the platform, although it can be a useful tool for some of the users.

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5.2 Use Cases

The use cases that outline the workflows in the scenarios presented above are the following.

Use Case 1: Integration of an existing open source software

- 1.1 The users need a tool to organise their bibliography.
- 1.2 This tool is not provided by the GoTRIPLE platform.
- 1.3 The user finds out that there is a non-commercial, open source tool that satisfies their needs.
- 1.4 The user proposes the tool to be integrated in the GoTriple platform.
- 1.5 The GoTriple Governance Team starts a discussion about integrating the tool to the platform, which takes place in the dedicated forum.
- 1.6 The community votes for the integration of the service to be part of the GoTriple platform.

Use Case 2: Integrating new resources

- 2.1. The users need to use resources that are not available in the GoTriple platform.
- 2.2 The user proposes the resources that could enrich the ones that already exist in the GoTriple platform.
- 2.3 The user contacts the institutions that have the resources in their collection to investigate the possibility of integrating these in the GoTriple platform.
- 2.4 The institutions consent to providing their content to the GoTriple.
- 2.5 The new resource calls for an extension of the GoTriple Vocabulary.
- 2.6. An information scientist assumes the task to make this extension.
- 2.7 The GoTriple Governance Team agrees to the extension of these resources, and new resources become part of the platform.

Use Case 3: Integrating a new, community-built service

- 3.1 The user is in need of an extension of one of the existing services.
- 3.2 After some research the user finds out that there is no such software available commercially.
- 3.3 The user enters the GoTriple forum to investigate if there are other users who have the same needs.
- 3.4 From the discussion in the forum it emerges that such an extension would be highly appreciated by a large part of the community.
- 3.5 A decision has to be made regarding the procedures of creation and governance of this plug-in.
- 3.5 The community decides that they are against the commercialization of the services.
- 3.6 The GoTriple Governance Team issues a call seeking volunteers to create the software.
- 3.7 A group of programmers assumes the task to create an open source software.
- 3.8 The group is accredited for the creation of this software by the GoTriple platform.

Use Case 4: User-made plug-in

- 4.1 The users have identified a set of data that is useful for their research, on the GoTriple platform.
- 4.2 They need to have digital tools in order to interpret the data 'in site'.
- 4.3 There is no such digital tool available.
- 4.4 They are, technologically, sophisticated enough to create their own software.
- 4.5 The software seems to be useful to other users too, so the creators propose that this software could be a permanent plug-in for the GoTriple platform.
- 4.6 A committee of experts inside and outside the TRIPLE Consortiums (the opinion of the TRIPLE members carries more weight) decide that this plug-in is useful and viable, and it could be a service of the platform.

Use Case 5: Integrating a proprietary software

5.1 The user needs software in order to manipulate the data in a way that provides the maximum information.

5.2 There is no commercial software available but there is one public.

5.3 The user asks the community if this could be a permanent plugin for the Gotriple platform.

5.4 Many users have objections because, although the software is useful, it is not entirely open source.

5.5 A mixed committee composed of the GoTriple Governance Team and users decides that the software cannot be a permanent plug-in since it is not entirely open-source.

DRAFT

6 | RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE GOVERNANCE OF FUTURE SERVICES

The aim of this part of the deliverable is to exploit the scenarios and use cases developed in this task in order to obtain actionable knowledge that can support decision-making regarding the governance of future services of the GoTriple platform

A main outcome of the research conducted for T3.5 is that open source software and platforms are highly appreciated not only by software and platform designers and developers themselves, but by the SSH community as well. This happens not only due to deontological but practical reasons as well. The participants in this research stated that for them openness is a value per se, although they realise that it cannot be applied in all circumstances, but they also stressed that an open source software can facilitate the interpretation of data in site, making their research easier and more effective. A general recommendation coming out of this research is: **promote open source solutions, as this will make the platform not only more attractive to the users, but it will also make it more adjustable to the users' needs.**

The research we conducted for T3.5 indicated that it is considered very important for users to have the opportunity to make contributions to the building of a platform. Through their interaction with a platform, users acquire knowledge and experience that can prove extremely valuable. Moreover they know their own needs better than the designers and developers, and they are in a position to propose or develop tools and services that can enrich the already existing ones. **It is recommended that users are allowed and encouraged to contribute to the development of future services. In accordance with their level of technological efficiency** some users can **report bugs**, others can **propose new resources** (i.e. data sets, publication, translations), and others can **create software and plug-ins** that will extend the GoTriple services.

Contributing to the cause of Open Science and open source software and the feeling that one belongs to a community that shares these values is a strong motivation for engaging in the task of extending the services and resources of a platform in general, and GoTriple in particular. Nevertheless a more personal reward to the people who contribute to the extension of the GoTriple platform may be an extra incentive. **It may be recommendable to have somewhere in the platform a proper mention (a star or a badge for example) of the users that have created a plug-in, etc.** This would be considered as a nice gesture of acknowledgement of their contribution, and on a more practical level, it would be a very good way for the creators to enhance their CV.

Regarding the governance procedures, what came out of this research is that users' opinions and insights should be taken into consideration. **It is highly recommended that users have a say in the decision-making regarding the integration of new services in the GoTriple platform.** Although users' opinions are considered valuable by all of the participants in this survey, there is no agreement regarding their degree of importance. One view is that users' opinion should carry the same weight as that of experts, in order to avoid an hierarchical structure of the

community. Another view is that experts, and especially experts who work on the GoTriple platform, know better what is feasible and really useful for the community, so their opinion should carry more weight.

One of the main recommendations coming out of this research is that users and experts must be in close collaboration. The GoTriple Governance Team together with users should create the necessary fora where they can collaborate in order to establish the best possible workflow and decision-making process for the enrichment of the GoTriple platform in a way that will make it more useful to the community of SSH and to all other interested parties.

7 | CONCLUSION

This deliverable summarises the findings of the research that was conducted for proposing the solutions for managing potential extensions of the GoTriple platform. Interviews and webinars with representatives of the academic community were conducted for this purpose and they led to the development of five scenarios and use cases that underpin the governance procedures for the implementation of new services or plug-ins to the GoTriple platform. The people that participated in this research are SSH researchers, programmers, librarians etc., but the key fact is that many of them have a dual background as SSH researchers and as developers or designers of research platforms or software.

The open resource character of the platform, the active participation of users in the extension of the platform and its services as well as in the decision-making regarding the governance of new services, and the interaction between users and experts are some of the main themes that emerged from this research. These themes provided the insights for the development of the main outcome of this research, the scenarios and the use cases.

The final outcome of the work that was done in T3.5 was the formulation of a set of recommendations regarding the ways in which future services can be incorporated in TRIPLE, as well as the governance of these services by the GoTriple Governance Team and the community.

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9 | APPENDIX

Interview Script for SSH Researchers Task 3.5

The GoTriple platform is an innovative multilingual and multicultural discovery solution for the social sciences and humanities (SSH). It will provide a central access point that will allow you to explore, find, access and reuse materials such as literature, data, projects and researcher profiles at European scale. It will not be a static platform, as new services will be integrated in the platform.

Users of the GoTriple platform will have the opportunity to propose tools and services for its enrichment. The purpose of this interview is: a) to explore what would be the appropriate governance processes that the TRIPLE community should adopt for the integration of future services and user generated tools (“plug-ins”) and b) identify the ways in which users themselves can enrich (e.g. with their own adaptations or plug-ins) the innovative tools provided by TRIPLE.

Questions:

Part I: Introductory Question

1. Just to begin the interview and to get to know you a bit better, we would like to know a little bit about yourself (age, stage of career, discipline) and the work that you do?

Part II: About Platforms in General

2. Can you tell us briefly what kind of software or platforms you normally use in your work? Especially software/platforms that are open source or are community driven? [If none, can you tell us why?]
3. How important is it for your work to have access to an open source platform that you can work with?
4. Have you ever contributed in any way to these open source software, their development or their improvement, or participated actively in the decision-making, or governance of this kind of development community? (if not) can you tell us why?

5. Do you think it is important for users to contribute to existing research software or platforms by proposing improvements, add-ons/plugin-ins to the existing services? Could you explain why?

Part III: About the TRIPLE Platform

6. In a similar way to the previous question: Can you tell us in your opinion what kind of contributions from users can help the GoTriple platform become more effective? or enhance its services? or new add-ons?
7. Would you be interested in contributing to the development of the GoTriple platform by proposing an adaptation or a plug in for one or more of the existing services?

Part IV: About the new services and their governance

8. In what way do you think that you could contribute to the GoTriple platform? Do you have in mind a possible adaptation for the GoTriple platform that you would like to see or that you could create?
9. Why would you engage yourself in such an effort? What would you expect from this?
10. What do you think would be the right procedures or processes that GoTriple should adopt in order for a user adaptation to be accepted and made available? Or, in other words, what is the workflow that should be put in place for deciding which user improvements should become part of the platform?
11. Who should be the members of the committee that will decide for the value and acceptance of the proposed plug in?
12. Would you think that a user who manages to produce an adaptation that is installed in the GoTriple platform should have some extra benefits? What kind of benefits could these be?
13. What do you think should be the model of governance for these new services? Should they be entirely open to the community without restrictions? Do you believe that openness is a value per se?

14. What is your opinion about copyright issues that may arise? Who owns the copyright of the proposed service (the person who created the plug in or TRIPLE)?

Conclusion

15. Is there something else you would like to add we have not covered in this interview?

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